

Ionic Conductivity in Complexes of Crosslinked Poly(ethylene oxide) and Alkali Thiocyanate

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The ion conducting polymer have attracted attention in recent years because of their properties and their potential applications. Wright first reported high ionic conductivity for mixture of poly(ethylene oxide) and alkali metal salts¹. Armand *et al.*² investigated their electrical properties and their behaviour as solid electrolytes². Since then polyether-alkali metal salt systems have been thoroughly studied during the past decade^{3,4}. Most of studies involved linear PEO with alkali metal salt. Here we report the preparation of two different types of crosslinked polymers based on poly(ethylene oxide) of molecular weight 1000 and 1500 respectively using POCl₃ as a cross-linking agent, then forming various complexes with alkali metal salts. The ionic conductivity of crosslinked PEO-1000/MSCN complexes is found higher than that of crosslinked PEO-1500/MSCN.

Results and Discussion

The salt contents in crosslinked polymer complex depend on the time for which crosslinked polymers are immersed in different concentrations of MSCN solution as revealed by ICP-analysis data shown in Table 1, for crosslinked PEO-1000/MSCN and PEO-1500/MSCN. From the general law expressing the ionic conductivity,

$$\sigma = unZF \quad (1)$$

F being the Faraday, Z the valence of the charge carriers, $n = \alpha C_0$ their concentration and u their mobility. The ionic conductivity should increase linearly with the square-root of the added salt concentration⁴. If dissociation is complete, the conductivity should obviously be proportional to the salt content⁴. In our study, the ionic conductivity firstly increases with the salt content. This behaviour is in agreement with eqn. (1). Then the maximum conductivity is observed in every system (Figs. 1 and 2). This is attributed to the compensation of two factors, namely, the carrier number and carrier mobility. The initial increase in the ionic conductivity is due to the increase in the carrier number, and the following decrease is explained in terms of the lower mobility due to the higher glass transition temperature. Previous studies¹⁻³ proposed that three phases coexist in PEO complex: the pure PEO crystal, the salt-rich stoichiometric crystalline complex and the amorphous phase. It is now generally accepted that crystalline phases do not contribute significantly to the ionic conductivity. The ionic conductivity of polymer complexes was con-

Fig. 1. Salt content dependence of ionic conductivity for crosslinked PEO-1000/MSCN complexes at 60°.

TABLE 1—SALT CONTENT IN CROSSLINKED PEO/MSCN COMPLEXES

Crosslinked polymer	MSCN	Immersed time h	Salt content MSCN/OE (mol)
POE-1000	LiSCN	1, 5, 9, 15, 48	0.016, 0.04, 0.10, 0.18, 0.24
	NaSCN	1, 5, 9, 15, 48	0.015, 0.04, 0.12, 0.18, 0.24
	KSCN	1, 5, 9, 15, 48	0.015, 0.043, 0.10, 0.17, 0.24
POE-1500	LiSCN	1, 3, 6, 12, 48	0.015, 0.039, 0.11, 0.17, 0.23
	NaSCN	1, 3, 6, 12, 48	0.014, 0.041, 0.11, 0.18, 0.24
	KSCN	1, 3, 6, 12, 48	0.016, 0.041, 0.11, 0.17, 0.24

Fig. 2. Salt content dependence of ionic conductivity for crosslinked PEO-1500/MSCN complexes at 60°.

tributed only by the amorphous phase in which the migratory activation is lowest. The amorphous fraction progressively increases with increasing salt concentration, the crystallinity becoming lower and lower⁵. X-Ray diffraction data for crosslinked PEO-1500/NaSCN sample containing different salt concentrations furnish a good evidence to the above proposal. In Fig. 3 there is a peak maximum at $Na^+/EO = 0.014$. As Na^+/EO ratio reached 0.041, the diffraction peak becomes lower. When Na^+/EO ratio increases to 0.18, there is only a peaky curve form. It means that the crosslinked PEO-1500/NaSCN shows amorphous structure in this condition and its ionic conductivity increases and then reaches a maximum. The salt content increased over the stoichiometric proportion of rich salt-crystal formation, and the degree of crystallinity of complexes was increased considerably. The ionic conductivity of the crosslinked PEO-MSCN complexes system decreased. Further inves-

Fig. 3. X-Ray diffraction patterns of crosslinked PEO-1500/MSCN complexes.

tigation into the nature of ionic conductivity in polymeric electrolytes has led to the conclusion that ion transport is strictly through the amorphous regions of these polymers, which tend to crystallise with a decreasing temperature. The temperature-dependence of ionic conductivities for crosslinked POE-MSCN complexes is shown in Fig. 4. All ionic conductivities of the crosslinked PEO-1000/MSCN are higher than that of crosslinked PEO-1500/MSCN under same conditions. The explanation is that the degrees of crystallinity are different in two complex systems^{5,6}. The X-ray diffraction results (Fig. 5) indicate that the crystallinity of the crosslinked PEO-1000/NaSCN is lower than that of the crosslinked PEO-1500/NaSCN under same salt concentration. It may explain the lower ionic conductivity of the latter. Table 2 shows the effect of different cations on the ionic conductivity. Our experimental data show the trend of the conductivity of the crosslinked POE-1000/MSCN ($M = Li, Na, K$) as $PEO-1000/KSCN > PEO-1000/NaSCN > PEO-1000/LiSCN$. The results are in good

Fig. 4. Temperature dependence of ionic conductivity in crosslinked PEO/MSCN complexes

agreement with the lattice energy order of alkaline metal salt.

Fig. 5. X-Ray diffraction patterns of crosslinked PEO-1000/NaSCN and crosslinked PEO-1500/NaSCN

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF DIFFERENT CATION ON IONIC CONDUCTIVITY

MSCN	Temp. °C	Ionic conductivity $\Omega \text{ cm}^{-1}$
LiSCN	60	9.85×10^{-7}
NaSCN	60	1.72×10^{-6}
KSCN	60	1.57×10^{-5}
LiSCN	80	1.76×10^{-6}
NaSCN	80	2.81×10^{-6}
KSCN	80	3.04×10^{-5}

Experimental

Poly(ethylene oxide) 1000 (PEO 1000) and poly(ethylene oxide) 1500 (PEO 1500) (Beijing Chemical Factory) were dried under vacuum at 120° for 2 h before use. Phosphorus oxychloride (extra-pure grade) was used as

NOTE

received. Acetone (B.C.F.) was dried with P_2O_5 and then distilled before use. Thiocyanates (MSCN; M = Li, Na, K) were dried by heating under vacuum at 140° for 5 h and used.

The reaction was carried out in a three-necked flask equipped with a mechanical stirrer, a water condenser and a pressure equalising dropping funnel. To an equivalent of PEO-1000 or PEO-1500 was added slowly three equivalents of phosphorus oxychloride under an argon atmosphere and stirred for 2 h at 80° . Then the solution was brought to solidify for 4 h at 100° . The obtained solid containing primarily low-MW polymers was washed with acetone (500 ml) and then allowed to dry under vacuum.

The resultant solids were immersed in a solution of acetone and MSCN at room temperature for different times. Then the solution was filtered. The obtained crosslinked PEO-1000/MSCN and PEO-1500/MSCN were dried using P_2O_5 under vacuum for 24 h.

X-Ray diffraction was performed with a D/max-3C (Rigaku, Japan) instrument. Conductivity was measured on pressed pellets of the polymer complex using a SR 530

lock-mampciter over the frequency 10 Hz. All of electrical measurements were performed at 20 – 120° . The ionic conductivity changed by two orders of magnitude over this temperature range. The ionic conductivity of crosslinked PEO-1000/KSCN was found to be 8.98×10^{-6} at 20° and $4.25 \times 10^{-4} (\Omega \text{ cm})^{-1}$ at 120° .

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